

URGENT ISSUES IN INDUSTRIAL PHARMACY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17310554>

Importance. The pharmaceutical industry is a crucial sector that encompasses the production of medicines, quality control, and technological processes. In recent years, the development of the local pharmaceutical industry has gained strategic importance due to global pandemics, the emergence of new diseases, increasing demand for medicines, and dependence on imports. Although this sector is rapidly developing in Uzbekistan, systemic problems still await resolution. Therefore, research conducted in this area serves the sustainable and competitive development of the pharmaceutical industry.

Research Objective. To identify the main problems in the pharmaceutical industry, analyze their causes and consequences, and develop scientifically based proposals for reforms in the sector.

Methods and Approaches. Analytical method: studying normative-legal documents, statistical data, and production indicators; Sociological method: conducting surveys among employees and experts of pharmaceutical manufacturing enterprises; Comparative method: comparing experiences of local and foreign pharmaceutical industries; SWOT analysis: identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the pharmaceutical industry.

Results. Many pharmaceutical products are still imported, which weakens the competitiveness of local manufacturers. There is a shortage of raw materials (API – active pharmaceutical ingredients) required for drug production. Technologies used in pharmaceutical manufacturing are outdated, and there is a lack of qualified engineer-technologists. Problems are observed in compliance with international GMP (Good Manufacturing Practice) standards. Lack of investments, especially for innovative projects, hinders the development of the sector.

Conclusions and Recommendations. Although the pharmaceutical industry is one of the important sectors, fully realizing its potential requires a systematic approach. The following measures are recommended: Developing local API production to reduce dependence on imported raw materials; Fully implementing GMP standards and strengthening control mechanisms; Integrating the specialist training system with the manufacturing process in the pharmaceutical sector; Expanding mechanisms to attract investments for innovative and modern technologies.